

THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS IN THE SELECTION OF PROJECTS IN INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. In this article, the aim is to study the market, to accelerate the marketing efforts of the manufactured products in the markets where they operate, to strengthen the effect of additional service after the sale of the goods, to search for opportunities to increase product sales, new market segments, consumers groups, installation of new models, search for new consumption or application areas for the manufactured product were considered.

Keywords: innovation, project, product, market, service, segment, model, efficiency.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada bozorni o'rganish, ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlarni faoliyat olib borilayotgan bozorlarda marketing harakatlarini jadallashtirish, tovarni sotishdan keyin qo'shimcha xizmat ko'rsatish ta'sirini kuchaytirish, mahsulot sotishni ko'paytirish imkoniyatlarini axtarishdir, bozorning yangi segmentlari, iste'molchilar guruhlari ga kirib borishini, yangi modellarni o'rnatish, ishlab chiqariladigan mahsulot uchun yangi iste'mol yoki tadbiriq sohalarini izlash ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalitli so'zlar: innovatsiya, loyiha, mahsulot, bozor, xizmat, segment, model, samaradorlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье целью является изучение рынка, ускорение маркетинговых усилий выпускаемой продукции на рынках, где она работает, усиление эффекта дополнительного обслуживания после продажи товара, поиск возможностей увеличения учитывались продажи продукции, новые сегменты рынка, группы потребителей, внедрение новых моделей, поиск новых областей потребления или применения выпускаемого продукта.

Ключевые слова: инновация, проект, продукт, рынок, услуга, сегмент, модель, эффективность.

In the development of our country's economy, the risk of innovative activity is defined as the probability of losses arising from investments in the creation and production of innovations. In order to reduce the risk in innovative activities, first of all, it is necessary to make a careful selection of the proposed projects. The importance of choosing innovative projects is determined by the following circumstances before the project:

Large-scale and high-level expenses for innovative innovations, limited funds allocated to specific areas of innovative innovations or topics, striving to select promising and relevant topics based on selection for high efficiency, proposals offered by customers and direct scientific and technical employees. It is important to reduce the scientific, technical and economic risks in order to reach the world level in the future in numerous topics, innovative innovations and research directions, it is important that the results of innovative innovations correspond to the strategies of enterprises.

Everyone knows that strategic planning determines the main directions of the activities of enterprises and firms, reflects the appropriate direction of all actions in the field of product production and sales. In Sungra, detailed plans are drawn up in each direction, because the results of enterprises and firms that apply the marketing concept are determined by the sales area, among the plans there is a special marketing planning that includes the processes of the movement of

goods from the creation of a copy of the product to the final sale. occupies the rank. The firm's growth opportunities consist of intensive, integrative, and diversified directions.

In the first group of options, the possibilities of development of the enterprise at the level of the existing scale and directions of production-market activity are determined. They have the appearance of intensive development of the enterprise itself. The second group of options includes the opportunities associated with the parts of the marketing system through integration, that is, the merger, and the third group includes opportunities that are not part of the marketing system, that is, diversification, that is, the opportunities that arise as a result of comprehensive expansion.

An intensive focus on development has not yet exploited its latent potential in product and market development

will be reasonable and specific to enterprises. Deep installation in the market - by studying the market, accelerating marketing efforts in the markets where the manufactured products are operating (for example: work to attract the buyer - lowering the price, increasing the effect of additional service after the sale of the goods) is to look for opportunities to increase product sales. The expansion of market areas involves the penetration of products into new geographical areas, i.e. in the country or abroad, into new market segments, consumer groups, and the search for new areas of consumption or application for the manufactured product.

Goods are improved by installing new models, producing types of products stratified by quality. The above-mentioned methods of intensive development can be considered in an alternative way, and they can also be interpreted in the form of activity stages. In the latter case, first attention is paid to activities aimed at accelerating market research efforts, then market expansion is attempted, and finally, if this effort is not profitable, the enterprise starts product development.

Options for integrated development are found in enterprises that have a solid position in their network and prospects for developing cooperation between the links of the marketing system within the network. In vertical integration, integration or global coordination occurs between certain links of the marketing system along the flow path.

Regressive or vertical integration implies that the manufacturer organizes its own production of raw materials together with the previous link or establishes strong cooperative relations with existing suppliers of raw materials. Along with the progressive or vertical integration link, the industrial enterprise moves to purchase or take control of wholesale and retail trade, that is, to reduce the costs of trade, eliminating the intermediate links of distribution and moving to the delivery of the product to the final consumer. zi means independent practice. Horizontal integration consists of mutual coordination of activities between enterprises standing at the same links of the marketing system. For example, two industries that produce the same product merge to increase the scale of production and at the same time reduce their costs. Such an association can be formed between wholesale or retail trade organizations, which in this way will raise their position in relation to suppliers and increase the volume of product sales.

Diversification development options groups believe that this behavior is the basis of enterprises that do not have opportunities for further growth within this marketing system and look for this opportunity outside this system.

There are three types of diversification: concentration, i.e. concentric diversification - occurs when the enterprise starts to produce a new product that is similar to the previous products of the firm from a technical or market point of view. For example, a company that manufactures

telephone equipment has increased its product range and switched to the production of answering machines or videophones. Thus, the company enriches its program and acquires a new group of consumers. Horizontal diversification is the transition to the production of new products that are technologically unrelated to the previously produced product.

The important tasks of choosing innovative projects are: correct selection of promising, relevant and effective directions, unknown, random and technical changes that are the subject of the future to take into account the inability to perform work on, to determine the reasons that reduce the scientific-technical and economic levels of the proposed innovations; to cover the costs of making methodological recommendations for the selection of projects to be accepted and approved based on the possibilities of innovation financing.

The experience of prospective and thematic planning of scientific and technical organizations and associations shows that it is not possible to create innovations using general, convenient methods of selecting projects, and in any case, it is necessary to develop a system of indicators for the effective implementation of evaluation. In the practical activity of selecting innovative projects, they can be supplemented with special indicators and methods of their calculation, methods that make the selection more accurate, determine the characteristics of the network and territory, goals and sources of topic formation.

When determining the system of indicators for the selection of the project, it is necessary to take into account the principle that the nature and content of the innovation correspond to the production - technical and financial capabilities of the branch enterprises. The principle of comprehensiveness of approaches is one of the important principles of choosing promising topics. The indicators are subject to the following requirements: logical connection with the final goals of the selected project, objectivity, simplicity and ease of calculation, accuracy and the same meaning of the obtained results, compliance with the accounting and reporting forms. The following group of indicators can be used for the selection of projects: scientific-technical, production-technological, financial-economic, social-ecological, network, legal, time indicators, market indicators.

A number of requirements are imposed on the methods of selecting innovative projects: strict selection of promising and more effective topics, compatibility of the results of the selected topics with the goals of the activity of the production-economy and science-production system, orientation of the selected topics to the goal, correct to have a high level of evaluation - first of all, to achieve the expected results and to evaluate the sources of formation of the topic correctly, to take into account the characteristics of the network and the region, etc.

Taking into account this complex of requirements is carried out through the complex use of various methods. The methods used in the selection of projects are divided into qualitative and quantitative methods. It is used in the selection of scientific and technical innovations in the initial stages:

1) Ability to implement planned innovations based on quality method, personal experience and competence. Increasing its objectivity is ensured by the use of well-organized expert evaluations and mathematical methods.

2) Table-analytical method, when using the table-analytical method in the selection of the project, first of all, the factors whose results are taken into account in the selection of topics are noted. From the point of view of UNIQUE methodology, a single set of factors is used for all methods of choosing a topic. Different grades (excellent, satisfactory, etc.) are used to describe the

effect of each factor to be selected. Only one assessment is given for each individual case.

3) Quantitative method - it is based on the use of a set of indicators of the application of a multi-level system of assessment.

By comparing different projects based on the obtained general indicators, it is possible to get a true assessment of the advantage of this or that innovative project. Newly constructed periodic graphs and tables, used or discovered during project implementation, are compared with original predictions. At the end, the actual results are compared with the initial assessment. Comparisons also showed that individual indicators changed positively or negatively. They can be useful from the point of view of experts who evaluate the projects and the best of them can be used in the selection of the project.

When applying quantitative methods, first-order indicators, key indicators for each specific topic are determined, their list is compiled and their values are determined. Every innovative organization or enterprise can use indicators that are useful and staffing for projects.

According to general indicators, topics are distributed in descending order of received sums, and their place in each topic is determined. In order to increase the level of reliability of the assessment, in addition to them in the distribution of subjects, the indicators are classified into categories depending on the sum of the obtained points, i.e. higher, first, and second level categories. Based on this, the initial selection of topics is made. In the implementation of innovative processes, an alternative choice based on several options is of great importance. In practice, increasing the economic efficiency of innovative processes serves to further develop and stabilize the economy of our country.

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